

Research Article

Neural processing of auditory stimuli in rats: Translational aspects using auditory oddball paradigms

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ABSTRACT

Background: The three-class oddball paradigm allows to investigate the processing of behaviorally relevant and irrelevant auditory stimuli. In humans, event-related potentials (ERPs) are used as neural correlate of behavior. We recorded local field potentials (LFPs) within the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) in rats during three-class and passive two-class oddball paradigms and analyzed the ERPs focusing on similarities to human recordings. **New method:** Rats were trained in a three-class auditory oddball paradigm to respond by nose poke to an infrequent Target tone that was rewarded, while ignoring an infrequent Distractor and frequent Standard tone of different frequencies. After reaching a success criterion of correct responses to the Target and correct rejection of the Standard and Distractor (80 %, each), electrodes were stereotaxically implanted into the mPFC. The recording of the neuronal activity took place in the three-class oddball paradigm as well as in a passive two-class oddball paradigm with unfamiliar frequencies.

Results: Correct responding to the Target tone was accompanied by a higher amplitude of the ERP in comparison to the Standard and Distractor tones ($p < 0.05$). Target Miss, or incorrect responding to Distractor or Standard led to reduced, respectively enhanced peak latency. In the two-class oddball paradigm, the amplitude of the Distractor ERP was enhanced as compared to that after Standard ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: ERPs derived from mPFC LFPs of rats show key characteristics similar to that derived from human EEGs. This model allows to investigate the processing of behaviorally important and irrelevant auditory stimuli in subcortical brain regions in a translational approach.

1. Introduction

We are constantly exposed to numerous environmental stimuli that needs to be classified into important and unimportant information, as only a small proportion of these stimuli are behaviorally relevant. Selective attention plays a crucial role in this context, but the neural mechanisms of how and where in the brain relevant versus irrelevant stimuli are prioritized are not yet fully understood [1]. The neural processing of incoming sensory information can be visualized by so-called event-related potentials (ERPs), which can be used as a measure of selective attention and cognitive processing of sensory

information. ERPs exhibit the highest amplitude when an event is particularly salient and receives focused attention [2,3]. The latency of ERPs is similarly affected, meaning that the easier the task or the identification of the stimulus, the shorter the latency. This parameter thus serves as a measure of the speed with which a stimulus is classified [4,5].

A typical setting to study attentional processing in humans is the auditory two-class oddball paradigm, which consists of a repetitive sequence of a “Standard tone” with specific acoustic properties that is infrequently interrupted by a rare tone with different acoustic properties. The oddball paradigm has also been used in several experimental

Abbreviations: ERPs, event-related potentials; LFPs, local field potentials; CR, correct rejection; FA, false alarm; MPFC, medial prefrontal cortex; EEGs, electroencephalograms; PFC, prefrontal cortex; BW, body weight; ITI, inter-trial-intervall; FP, false poke; IR, infrared.

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settings [6]. In the passive setting, the rare tone is unconsciously mapped as a "Deviant" exhibiting a larger ERP amplitude, whereas in the active paradigm the subjects actively respond to deviant stimuli [7–9]. As the rare tone is unconsciously mapped as "Deviant", the passive oddball paradigm can be used in anaesthetized rats [10,11], or in awake, freely moving rats to assess the neurophysiological correlate of deviant detection [12]. The active oddball paradigm can be used to study the behavioral response to deviants of certain characteristics following behavioral training [13].

The auditory three-class oddball paradigm, on the other hand, consists of a sequence of frequent Standard tones and two infrequent deviant tones. One of the two deviant tones is defined as the relevant "Target" requiring a behavioral response, whereas the infrequent "Distractor" must be ignored. Thus, discriminating between Target and Distractor tones in the three-class oddball paradigm requires conscious allocation of attention to different stimuli against the background of the Standard tone. Although structurally similar, the two-class and the three-class paradigms require different cognitive and sensory demands and engage different neural mechanisms. Whereas the response to the deviant in the two-class oddball paradigm is mostly driven by bottom-up processes, the three-class oddball paradigm depends mostly on top-down control involving task-specific learning and decision-making pathways [14]. Recognition of the behaviorally relevant information (Target tone) is accompanied by a large and late ERP, whereas the ERP following an infrequent Distractor tone, which must be ignored, is smaller [9]. The processing of auditory stimuli using the three-class oddball paradigm has mostly been studied with ERPs derived from human electroencephalograms (EEGs), although ERPs derived from local field potentials (LFPs) recorded from intracranial electrodes in human patients undergoing deep brain stimulation (DBS) surgery have also been used [9,15,16]. However, it is the clinical need, not the scientific question that determines which brain regions are used for these recordings after implantation of DBS electrodes.

The prefrontal cortex (PFC) is involved in higher levels of information processing, plays a key role in associative-limbic brain circuits, and is anatomically and functionally connected to the auditory pathway [10,17]. Using passive auditory oddball paradigms in anaesthetized rats, it has already been shown that ERPs can be derived in the medial PFC (mPFC) and that auditory responsiveness is driven by unpredictability, while suppressing redundant input more efficiently than the auditory cortex [10,11].

The auditory three-class oddball paradigm has already been implemented in rats to study operant learning in an animal model of mutism [18]. While human subjects pressed a button after the Target tone [9,15,16], the rats were trained to interrupt a light barrier with their nose in response to the Target tone, whereupon they were rewarded with a casein pellet [18]. Our aim was to test whether ERPs derived from neural recordings in the mPFC of rats during behavioral testing in the three-class auditory oddball paradigm would exhibit characteristics similar to those recorded in humans. A passive two-class auditory oddball paradigm using novel frequencies was also applied in awake freely moving rats.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Animal husbandry

Male Sprague Dawley rats (Charles River Laboratories, $n = 9$, > 200 g at start of training) were used for this study. The animals were housed in groups of 2–3 animals in a Makrolon Type IV cage within a scintainer (Scanbur) under controlled environment ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; $55 \pm 10\%$ humidity; 10/14 h dark/light cycle with lights on at 06:00 am) and with access to water all times. Standard rodent chow (Altromin, Lage, Germany) was fed with 16 g per day per animal to enhance salience of reward pellets during behavioral testing while still ensuring weight gain until 400–500 g body weight (BW). Clinical scores

and BW were measured at least two times a week to ensure the well-being of the rats. All experiments were carried out in accordance with the EU directive 2010/63, were approved by the local animal ethics committee (Lower Saxony State Office for Consumer Protection and Food Safety # AZ 17/2583), and complied with ARRIVE guidelines. All efforts were undertaken to minimize the number of animals used and their suffering.

2.2. Course of the study

Rats were first trained in the three-class oddball paradigm, thereafter implanted with electrodes in the mPFC for cable-bound recording during behavioral testing (Fig. 1A). Neuronal recording in the three-class oddball paradigm was done in three sessions, and finally in the two-class oddball paradigm in awake, free moving rats (Fig. 1B). Electrode's position in the mPFC was verified in Nissl-stained sections.

2.3. Oddball paradigm

The three-class auditory oddball paradigm was conducted in rat 5/9-hole boxes (80600 A Operant Chamber, Campden Instruments Limited, Loughborough, UK) with one open hole located on the back panel and a small container with a flap in the front panel for reward pellets (Dustless Precision Pellets 45 mg, Rodent Purified Diet BioServ) provided by a food magazine. Infrared (IR) sensors detected nose-pokes into the back hole, or when the rat took the pellet out of the container. The stimulus schedules and the data acquisition were controlled by the software Presentation (Neurobehavioral Systems Inc.®), which also sent information to a microcontroller (Arduino) that controls the feeder's stepper motor.

During the three-class oddball paradigm, the rat had to respond to a Target tone (5000 Hz) by a nose poke while ignoring a frequent Standard tone (3000 Hz), and an infrequent Distractor tone (1500 Hz), i.e., frequencies that had also been used in human studies [9,15,16]. Standard, Target and Distractor tones, all 100 ms, were presented with sound level of 80 ± 10 dB in a ratio of 60:20:20 followed by a response time window (trial duration) of 3000 ms. Between tone signals, an inter-trial interval (ITI) randomly set between 1500 and 2500 ms was introduced. Responding or ignoring a Target tone led to a Target "Hit" or a Target "Miss" count, respectively. Correct ignoring a Standard or Distractor tone led to a correct rejection (CR) count (S-CR and D-CR, respectively). False responding to a Standard or Distractor was counted as a false alarm (S-FA and D-FA, respectively). Responding in the ITI was counted as a false poke (FP), followed by a timeout of 1000 ms as "punishment". A schematic overview of the three-class oddball design and the corresponding parameters are shown in Fig. 1C.

For the three-class oddball paradigm, animals were trained for several weeks prior to stereotaxic implantation of the electrodes into the mPFC. First, the rats were familiarized with the box and the reward pellets in habituation sessions on two consecutive days. Training of the rats begun the following day with a maximum duration of 60 min or 100 completed trials. Initially, the Target tone had a duration of 7000 ms, with a maximum allowed response time of 7000 ms. Once the rat answered these Target tones 80 % correctly, the stimuli duration and the maximum reaction time to the stimuli were successively reduced to the final duration of 100 ms and a reaction time of 3000 ms. Meanwhile, the Standard tone and the Distractor tone were introduced successively. As the main difficulty for the rats during training was not to poke prematurely, a timeout wait interval of up to 10 s was introduced after an incorrect response. The training goal for the paradigm was reached when the rat correctly responded to the Target tone and simultaneously ignored the Standard and Distractor tones by 80 %, each.

For the passive two-class oddball paradigm, the rats were placed in an open field box (Square box, length: 60 cm). Here, two tones of unfamiliar frequencies (100 ms each) were presented; a frequent Standard tone (8000 Hz) and an infrequent Distractor tone (13300 Hz). The ratio

Fig. 1. Experimental Design. A shows a rat with cable-bound recording during the auditory oddball paradigm. B presents a graphical timeline of the procedures in the experiment. C shows a schematic overview of the three-class oddball design and D the two-class paradigm with the corresponding parameters (for detailed information see section Methods). E shows a Nissl-stained section and a schematic drawing showing the tips of the recording electrodes in the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) region. Abbreviations: CR: correct rejection, FA: false alarm.

of the tones was 95:5 % presented in pseudo random sequence with an ITI of 400 ms. A schematic overview of the two-class oddball design and the corresponding parameters are shown in Fig. 1D.

2.4. Electrode implantation surgery

The surgery was performed under general chloral hydrate anesthesia (360 mg/kg) with local anesthesia (Lidocaine) and systemic analgesia (Carprofen: 5 mg/kg intraoperatively, 2.5 mg/kg postoperatively for two days). The antibiotic Marbofloxacin (Marbocyl®: 6.6 mg in 1 ml/kg) was given subcutaneous for eight days starting two days before surgery. Rats were placed in a stereotactic apparatus (Stoelting, Wood Dale, IL, USA) with atraumatic ear bars and tooth bar set at -3.3 mm during surgery. A unipolar electrode of insulated platinum-iridium wire (90:10; 101R-3T; Science-Products GmbH), coated with Teflon (uncoated \varnothing 76 μ m, coated \varnothing 140 μ m, A-M SYSTEMS, Inc., Carlsborg, USA) was handmade in our laboratory. The wire was covered in a 13 mm long cylinder (outer \varnothing : 0.45 mm; inner \varnothing : 0.25 mm, Sterican Braun Melsungen AG, Germany) and an uncoated wire tip was exposed by 0.45 – 0.5 mm. All animals were implanted with an electrode in the right mPFC (Coordinates: Anterior-Posterior: $+2.7$ mm, Lateral: -0.8 mm, Dorso-Ventral: -4.4 mm from skull, referring to bregma). A jeweler's screw with attached wire was inserted near the recording

electrode and used as reference. Additionally, a wire attached jeweler's screw was inserted into the skull above the cerebellum to serve as the ground electrode. All implants were attached with dental acrylic (Paladur®) to anchor screws. A head-stage connector was formed to allow recording of neuronal activity via a flexible cable in the awake, freely moving rat during the behavioral experiment. All rats were monitored on a warming mat until full awakening. After surgery, the rats were kept in individual cages overnight and then returned to their cage mates.

2.5. Electrophysiology recording

For neuronal recordings, the rat head-stage was connected with a cable to the electrode adaptor box. A swivel was interposed to allow free movement during behavioral testing. LFP signals were amplified 1000-fold using isolated amplifiers (Cambridge Electronic Design CED 1902), band-limited (band pass, 0.5 – 100 Hz) and digitized (Cambridge Electronic Design CED 1401 Mark II) with a resolution of 1000 Hz, and saved for further computations (Spike II software v.6). From the digitized signals, 50 Hz frequency was removed with a notch filter. Neuronal signals were synchronized with auditory stimuli of the oddball paradigm as trigger events, while rat behavioral responses (nose-poke) were tracked by the Presentation® software. All behavioral responses and event marker information were then sent to Spike2 with a specific code

through the amplifier (CED 1401) and displayed real time on the computer together with the brain activity. For the three-class oddball paradigm three sessions per animal were recorded, two with 400 trials, and one session with 1000 trials. Finally, neural recordings during the two-class oddball paradigm took place in an open field with 500 trials.

2.6. Data processing

All data processing steps were done using PC (Windows 10). For the behavioral data of the animals the text files extracted by Presentation® software were used to extract the number of correct and incorrect responses to Target, Distractor and Standard and organized in percentage of correct/incorrect responses. In addition, the reaction time to nose pokes in the back hole was measured for correct responses to Target Hit, respectively for incorrect responses to Standard and Distractor FA. The distribution of behavioral reaction times was visualized and characterized by box plots showing the median, as well as the 25–50 % and the 10–90 % percentiles.

For the acquisition of the ERP data the software Python with the PyCharm community Editor was used, the extraction of data from Spike to Python was done with the packages Neo and NumPy. At first, the data was distributed to their associated variables stored as NumPy Arrays. Raw data were filtered offline with a lowpass filter of 30 Hz (as done in [15]) and epoched from –200–800 ms around stimulus onset (three-class oddball paradigm) or from –200–500 ms for the two-class oddball paradigm. The first step in the peak detection analyses was to select appropriate time windows for the ERP components based on visual inspection. To do this, the individual ERPs of the different conditions (correct and incorrect responses to the Target, Distractor and Standard tones) were visualized for each rat to define our areas of interest. Only correct trials were included in the peak detection analysis to ensure that the peak amplitudes of all rats fell within the defined area.

After defining the time windows, the local peak minimum and maximum for the ERPs were calculated with our defined areas of interest using the grand average of all animals. For the grand average data, all trials were treated equally by creating a mean. For both oddball paradigms all individual ERPs were normalized by subtracting the mean of the data, followed by the dividing of the standard deviation of the data. Trials greater than three times the standard deviation in the baseline recording (–200–0 ms) were discarded. Next, the peak of the ERPs, on rat level, for correct and incorrect responding to Target, Distractor and Standard were calculated. The highest value within a ± 10 ms window around the peak of the grand average was determined and calculated for each animal and its corresponding trials. The latency of the trials was calculated similarly, defined as the time of the local maximum or minimum, with a variation ± 10 ms. This applies to both the early and the late component, also considering its polarity.

2.7. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses were performed with SigmaPlot15 (Systat Software GmbH). For the reaction time a Friedman repeated measures ANOVA with post-hoc comparison Tukey test in case of significance was used. For the three-class oddball paradigm, the mean of the amplitude and the peak latency of the early and late component of the ERPs for each rat was analyzed by Two-way repeated measure (RM) ANOVA with condition (Target, Distractor, and Standard) as 1st factor and behavior (correct or incorrect) as 2nd factor. ANOVA was followed by Post-hoc comparison of groups in case of significance ($p < 0.05$) with Bonferroni *t*-test. For the two-class oddball paradigm the amplitude and peak latencies of the ERP after Standard and Distractor tones were analyzed by a paired *t*-test. All tests were performed two-sided and $p < 0.05$ was considered to be significant. Graphs of the behavioral data and the peak latencies and amplitudes were conducted using GraphPad Prism 10 (GraphPad Software, Inc, 2023). All ERP Graphs were made with Python using Matplotlib. Bar charts were created using GraphPad Prism 10

(GraphPad Software, Inc, 2023).

3. Results

All nine animals were successfully trained for correct performance of 80 % within 6–9 weeks (about 35 training sessions) and were subjected to stereotaxic implantation of electrodes. All rats recovered from surgery without substantial weight loss or clinical side effects. During retraining rats adapted quickly to their previous level of training. For analysis of electrophysiological recordings during the three-class oddball paradigm a level of 70 % correct responses to Target, respectively correct rejection of Standard and Distractor was accepted. During the three recording sessions, four rats did not reach the level of 70 % for either correct response to Target, respectively, correct rejection of Distractor and Standard in one session, which were therefore excluded from further analysis. Moreover, one rat lost its head-stage. Therefore, for the three-class oddball paradigm, 22 sessions of 9 rats were used for behavioral and electrophysiological analysis and for the two-class oddball paradigm recordings of 8 rats could be used.

3.1. Behavior

All recording sessions together a Hit rate of $90 \% \pm 0.017$ SEM was reached, while the Distractor and Standard was correctly rejected by $89 \% \pm 0.014$ SEM and $83 \% \pm 0.015$ SEM (Fig. 2A). The reaction time was analyzed for Target Hit ($n = 1935$) and for false alarms (FAs) to Distractor and Standard ($n = 232$ and $n = 1716$) in the three-class oddball-paradigm sessions (Fig. 2B). The rats responded precisely to the Target Hit (median of the reactions after 1323 ms with 80 % of the responses in a time window of 1138 ms). Although the median of the reaction times of false responding the Standard and Distractor tones were similar to that after Target (median of 1378 ms after Standard and 1519 after Distractor), the reaction times were more widespread, i.e., 80 % of the reactions in a time window of 2242 ms for the Distractor, and 1959 ms for the Standard. Comparing the interquartile range (IQR) for all three tones with Friedman ANOVA revealed a significant difference among the groups ($\chi^2=16.222$; $df = 2$; $p < 0.001$). Post hoc pairwise comparisons (Tukey test) indicated that responding to the Target is significantly differed from Distractor ($p < 0.001$) and Standard ($p = 0.048$), whereas reaction times after Distractor and Standard did not differ ($p = 0.225$).

3.2. Analysis of ERPs

3.2.1. Three-class oddball paradigm

Based on visual inspection of the individual ERPs a time window of 50–190 ms was used for the early, and of 200–450 ms for the late peak component of the ERP. After reduction of the ERPs (see 2.6 methods section) 13337 trials were included, attributed to Target Hit ($n = 1810$), Distractor CR ($n = 1785$), Standard CR ($n = 7744$), Target Miss ($n = 184$), Distractor FA ($n = 214$) and Standard FA ($n = 1600$). The grand average ERPs of correct and incorrect behavior to Target, Distractor and Standard is shown in Fig. 3A. The bar charts represent the ERPs on animal level, creating a mean per animal ± 10 ms around the grand average high point of each area of interest. Comparison of the early ERP component showed that the amplitudes per animal were highest for the Target stimulus, both compared to Target Miss and to correct or incorrect responding to Distractor and Standard (Fig. 3B). Two-way RM ANOVA showed significant effects for the factor condition ($F_{2, 16} = 19.744$, $p < 0.001$), while the factor behavior and the interaction between factors were not significant (both $F > 2.4$, $p > 0.13$). Post-hoc comparison showed that within correct behavior the amplitude for Distractor and standard was reduced compared to Target ($p < 0.001$). Within incorrect behavior, the amplitude of the Distractor was reduced compared to Target ($p = 0.007$). Comparison between correct and incorrect responses showed that the amplitude after

Fig. 2. Behavioral results. A shows the ratio for the correct behavior (%) for all tones, i.e. for Target Hit (red), and correct rejection of Distractor (blue) and Standard (green). Data are shown as mean \pm S.E.M. with the individual data points. B shows the box plots (10 – 90 percentile) with median of the reaction time as well as the single values for Target, respectively for the reaction time of false alarms to Distractor and Standard. Significant difference of the interquartile range ($p < 0.05$) to Target is visualized by asterisk (*; Friedman repeated measures ANOVA followed by post-hoc comparison with Tukey test).

incorrect response to the Target was reduced as compared to Target Hit ($p = 0.024$, see Fig. 3B).

For the latency of the early ERP component the two-way RM ANOVA showed significant effects for the factor condition ($F_{2, 16} = 138.999$, $p < 0.001$) and for the interaction between factors condition and behavior ($F_{2, 8} = 88.112$, $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc comparison showed that the latency of the Distractor and Standard was prolonged as compared to the Target for both correct and incorrect behavior (all $p < 0.05$). However, while the latency of for the Standard was highest within correct responses, this measure was reduced compared to that of the Distractor for the incorrect responses ($p < 0.05$; see Fig. 3C). While the latency of Target and Standard was reduced for incorrect behavior ($p < 0.05$) the latency for Distractor was enhanced ($p < 0.05$, see Fig. 3C).

The amplitude of the late ERP component was highest after correct responses to the Target. Also, false alarms to the Distractor were accompanied by an enhanced amplitude. Statistical analysis with a two-way RM ANOVA showed significant effects for the factor condition ($F_{2, 16} = 5.412$, $p = 0.016$), while the factor behavior and the interaction between factors were not significant (factor behavior: $F = 4.010$, $p = 0.080$; Interaction: $F = 0.929$, $p = 0.415$). Post-hoc comparison showed that within correct behavior the amplitude for Distractor and Standard was reduced compared to Target ($p < 0.05$), while within incorrect behavior no group difference was shown. Comparison between correct and incorrect responses, however, showed that the amplitude after incorrect response to the Distractor was enhanced ($p < 0.05$, see Fig. 3B).

Analysis of the late ERP peak latency showed shortest latencies for the Distractor and Standard within correct behavior, while peak latencies were enhanced after false alarms to Distractor and Standard. A two-way RM ANOVA showed significant effects for the factor condition ($F_{2, 16} = 39.522$, $p < 0.001$) and for the interaction between factors condition and behavior ($F_{2, 8} = 49.872$, $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc comparison within correct behavior showed that the latency of the Target was longest as compared to the Distractor and Standard (all $p < 0.05$), while for the incorrect behavior no significance was found. While after Target Miss the latency was reduced ($p < 0.05$), incorrect responding to the Distractor and Standard was followed by an enhanced latency compared to correct responding (both $p < 0.05$; Fig. 3C).

3.2.2. Two-class oddball paradigm

The grand average of the two-class oddball paradigm ERPs are shown in Fig. 3D. Analysis of the early and late component of the ERP showed enhanced amplitudes and shortened latencies for the infrequent Distractor as compared to the frequent Standard tone. Paired t-test showed a significance for late ERP amplitude as well as for both ERP latencies

(all $p < 0.05$). The amplitude of the Distractor was similar to that measured after Distractor in the three-class oddball paradigm (Fig. 3E-F).

4. Discussion

Oddball paradigms are used to study information processing related to attention, decision-making and cognition. In human studies, ERPs are typically derived from EEGs recorded at the head surface [8]. The early component of the ERP following an oddball sequence decreases for predictable stimuli, but increases for novel or unpredictable stimuli. The late component is associated with higher cognitive processes and is enhanced by conscious attention to the stimuli. In contrast to the two-class oddball paradigm, the three-class oddball paradigm requires conscious discrimination between two rare deviant tones within a sequence of frequent Standard tones. One of the two deviant tones is defined as the relevant Target, which requires a behavioral response, whereas the rare Distractor must be ignored. In humans, the accompanying grand average ERP is typically characterized by a large early component, the N1 component, which occurs approximately 100 ms after the tone signals, and a later P3 component, which occurs approximately 300 ms after the tones. The deviant Distractor and Target tones elicit an enhanced early N1 amplitude compared to the Standard tone [19], while the late P3 component of the ERP upon Target has a higher amplitude and a longer peak latency than that of the Distractor tone [8, 20, 21]. The late P3 is therefore considered to be a long-latency cognitive component, representing the time it takes to classify the target stimulus [4, 5].

Our group has shown that by using the auditory three-class oddball paradigm, ERPs can also be obtained from LFPs recorded from electrodes implanted in specific brain regions of patients undergoing DBS. This innovative approach has facilitated a deeper understanding of the role of different subcortical brain regions in the processing of relevant and irrelevant auditory information [9, 15, 16]. Using the three-class oddball paradigm, we showed that neuronal activation in the human centromedian-parafascicular complex precedes and predicts cortical responses to behaviorally relevant auditory target events, but not to irrelevant distractor or standard tones [15]. However, neuronal recordings from DBS electrodes are limited to brain regions targeted for clinical purposes and are only feasible during a short postoperative period when the electrodes are externalized. These limitations do not apply to experimental research, where rodent models allow the targeting of specific brain regions to better understand the neurobiological mechanisms involved in cognitive processes. The mPFC is of particular interest in this regard, as it is critical for higher-order cognitive

Fig. 3. Electrophysiological ERP results. A shows the grand average ERPs for the correct (left) and the incorrect (right) responses. B-C show bar graphs (mean ± S.E.M) of the amplitudes (B) and peak latencies (C) for the early component of the ERP measured between 50 – 190 ms, and for the late component measured between 200 – 450 ms. Significance differences to Target within correct or incorrect behavior are shown as asterisks (* p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001 after two-way repeated measure (RM) ANOVA), significance difference within the factor stimuli are shown as diamond (# p < 0.05; ## p < 0.01; ### p < 0.001 Bonferroni *t*-test). D shows the grand average ERPs obtained in the two-class oddball paradigm. E-F show bar graphs (mean ± S.E.M) of the amplitudes (E) and peak latencies (F) for the early and late component. Significance differences between Standard and Distractor are shown as asterisks (* p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001; Paired *t*-test). Abbreviations: CR: correct rejection, FA: false alarm.

processing and is anatomically connected to virtually all sensory and motor systems, as well as to subcortical associative-limbic brain circuitries [22–26].

In the present study, we used rats to record neural activity in the mPFC during the three-class oddball paradigm. Rats were trained to respond to a Target tone, while ignoring a rare deviant and a frequent Standard tone with parameters that were comparable to those used in the human context. With regard to the peak latency of the late ERP component, our findings in rats were similar to those in humans. The peak latency of the late ERP after the target was the longest, followed by that of the distractor and standard, confirming that the late ERP is a cognitive component with a long latency, representing the time taken to classify a target stimulus. Also similar to findings in humans, the amplitude of both the early and late components of the ERP following the Target tone was greater than that elicited by the Standard and Distractor tones. However, in our experimental setting the amplitudes of

Standard and Distractor did not differ. This differs from findings in humans, where early ERPs show high amplitudes for both distractors, and late ERPs show highest amplitudes for the target, followed by distractor and standard. It should be noted that rats in the three-class oddball paradigm are trained for 6–8 weeks to reach 80 % performance. Therefore, the rats are probably overtrained with respect to the deviant distractor tone.

In line with this, studies in humans and animals have shown that neuronal populations responding to a certain stimulus undergo adaptation with repeated exposure [27–29]. It has also been shown that neurons of the mPFC cease responding to deviant stimuli when their occurrence is expected [30–32]. Using a passive oddball paradigm in anesthetized rats, it has also been shown that the mPFC effectively suppresses redundant input [10]. Interestingly, in the present study, when two unknown frequencies were presented to our rats as a passive two-class oddball paradigm, the early ERP component had a larger

amplitude upon the infrequent deviant than upon the frequent Standard tones, and only the deviant tone elicited a substantial late ERP amplitude. This finding also highlights a key difference in the concept of the active three-class oddball compared to the passive two-class oddball paradigm. In the auditory two-class oddball paradigm a sequence of frequent Standard tones is infrequently interrupted by rare tones that are unconsciously mapped as "Deviant". This paradigm can therefore be applied without prior training and even in anaesthetized rats [10]. Our results show that presenting the two-class oddball paradigm to awake, freely moving rats yields similar results to those obtained in anaesthetized rats. However, direct comparisons between the two studies are not entirely valid as different frequencies and intertrial intervals were used.

An important difference between humans and rats is that after instruction, humans readily perform the three-class oddball test with high accuracy of almost 100 %, whereas rats must be trained for weeks to respond correctly to the target while ignoring the standard and distractor tones at least 80 % of the time. Nevertheless, this allowed us to analyze the ERPs upon false responses in more detail. We hypothesized that a false classification of the different tone signals would be accompanied by reduced amplitudes and reduced peak latencies after Target, whereas an incorrect response to Standard or Distractor would result in enhanced amplitudes and prolonged peak latencies. Indeed, after Target Miss the early component of the ERP had a lower amplitude compared to Target Hit. Also, in line with our expectations, incorrect responses to Standard or Distractor resulted in increased peak latencies of the late ERP component. This finding may be the result of conscious misinterpretation of the tones and is consistent with the theory that the late P3 is a long-latency cognitive component, represented by the time to classify the tone signals into Target, Distractor or Standard. However, the amplitudes following incorrect responses to Distractor and Standard were not enhanced, which somewhat contradicts this assumption. In this context, analysis of the behavioral reaction time for incorrect responses to Standard and Distractor showed that the response was, at least in part, the result of random nose poking during the response window of three seconds after the tone signals, whereas the correct responding to the Target tone occurred exactly one second after the tone onset.

Although we have shown that neural recordings during the three-tone auditory oddball in awake, freely moving rats are feasible and allow the extraction of ERPs with key features similar to those derived from humans, there are several limitations that need to be addressed. We used frequencies for Target, Distractor and Standard that are optimal for humans and thus have been used previously in our human settings [9,15,16], but are not within the optimal hearing range of rats [33]. However, it has been shown that rats reliably respond to low frequencies from 1000 Hz on, whereas the loudness of frequencies < 1000 Hz need to be much higher to elicit a behavioral response [34]. In addition, it has been shown that when animals are trained with pure tones, the threshold is lowered [35]. Nevertheless, we used novel frequencies for the two-class oddball paradigm because the rats had been trained for weeks with the frequencies used for the three-class oddball paradigm, and we anticipated neural adaptation to these frequencies. Another limitation may be that - in contrast to our previous studies in humans [9,15,16] - the intertrial intervals used in the three-class oddball paradigm were randomly set. However, after a Target tone, the rat needs 1000–2000 ms for a behavioral response, after which it had to turn around to get the reward pellet. Therefore, we used a longer response time in our rat study compared to our human setting. In addition, rats show impulsive nose-poking in the inter-trial interval during training, which has to be counteracted by introducing a 'wait' interval as a punishment. In summary, using rats, it was not possible to implement a short and equal intertrial interval in the three-class oddball paradigm. A final limitation is that we used different ratios for tone signals in the two- and three-class paradigms. It has been shown that the rarer the deviant stimulus, the greater the effect of novelty detection [3]. We therefore used a ratio of 95:5 for Standard and Distractor in the two-class paradigm. In the

three-class oddball paradigm, however, we were also interested in false alarms. In order to ensure a sufficiently large number of false responses with training for 80 % correct responses, we used a ratio of 20:60:20.

5. Conclusion

Together, we showed that neural recordings during auditory oddball in awake free moving rats are feasible and allow to extract ERPs with key characteristics similar to that derived from humans. Differences in the neuronal responses mainly concerned the infrequent Distractor tone, which can be explained by a certain over-training of the rat with respect to this stimulus. Notably, using the three-class oddball paradigm in rats with accuracy of 80 % also allows to evaluate the neurophysiological correlate of the incorrect behavior. Using the three-class oddball paradigm may therefore be valuable to investigate cognitive processes and the underlying neuronal activity in brain regions not accessible in humans. It allows to examine where in the brain the distinction between relevant and irrelevant deviants occurs, also with regard to the interactions between brain regions under normal and pathological conditions.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Katharina Korb: Software. **Jonas Jelinek:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology. **Mesbah Alam:** Investigation, Methodology. **Franck Fogaing Kamgaing:** Software. **Franziska M. Decker:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Elvis J. Hermann:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision. **Joachim K. Krauss:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Kerstin Schwabe:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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